

Health Impact of Climate Change: Focuses on How Global Warming and Related Environmental Changes Impact Public Health, Including the Spread of Infectious Diseases, Food Security and Chronic Health Conditions

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Abstract:

Background: Climate change, driven by rising global temperatures and increased frequency of extreme weather events, poses significant threats to public health. These impacts are evident in the changing distribution of infectious diseases, compromised food security, and exacerbation of chronic health conditions.

Aim: This study aims to assess the health effects of climate change on the local population in Gaya, focusing on the prevalence of infectious diseases, food insecurity, and chronic health conditions.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted over six months at the Department of Community Medicine at ANMMCH, Gaya, involving 300 participants selected through random sampling. Data were collected via structured interviews and questionnaires covering demographic information, health status, and climate-related exposures. Statistical analyses, including chi-square tests and logistic regression, were performed using SPSS version 23.0 to identify significant associations and predictors of adverse health outcomes.

Results: The study found that 60% of participants were exposed to extreme heat events, and 30% experienced infectious diseases. A significant association was observed between extreme heat exposure and infectious diseases ($\chi^2(1) = 4.76, p = 0.029$). Additionally, 40% of participants faced food insecurity, which was significantly associated with chronic health conditions ($\chi^2(1) = 5.14, p = 0.023$). Logistic regression identified age, extreme heat exposure, and food insecurity as significant predictors of adverse health outcomes.

Conclusion: The findings underscore the multifaceted health impacts of climate change, particularly in terms of increased infectious diseases and chronic health conditions. Addressing these challenges requires integrated public health strategies and policies focusing on climate mitigation and adaptation.

Recommendations: Future public health initiatives should prioritize enhancing community resilience to climate-related health risks, improving food security, and developing targeted interventions to mitigate the health impacts of extreme weather events.

Keywords: Climate Change, Public Health, Infectious Diseases, Food Security, Chronic Health Conditions.

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Introduction

Rising global temperatures, changed precipitation patterns, and a rise in the frequency of extreme weather events are all signs of climate change, which is a serious and complicated issue with significant effects on public health. The scientific community is in agreement that human activity—specifically, the release of greenhouse gases—is the primary cause of the notable alterations in the Earth's climate system (IPCC, 2018) [1]. Global populations are impacted by these climate shifts, with vulnerable communities suffering the most from both direct and indirect health concerns.

The distribution and prevalence of infectious diseases have changed, which is one of the most obvious and direct implications of climate change on public health. Increased temperatures and changed precipitation patterns have the potential to spread vector-borne illnesses like dengue fever and malaria into previously untouched. Moreover, by contaminating water sources and overloading sanitation infrastructure, extreme weather events like hurricanes and floods can cause outbreaks of waterborne infections (Watts et al., 2019) [2].

Chronic health issues like respiratory and cardiovascular disorders are also related to climate

change. One major risk factor for these illnesses is air pollution, which is made worse by rising temperatures and a rise in the frequency of wildfires. According to the World Health Organisation (WHO, 2021) [3], air pollution has serious negative effects on health and causes millions of early deaths every year. Furthermore, the effects of climate change on psychological and mental health, such as anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) after extreme weather events, are becoming more widely acknowledged as serious public health issues (Hayes et al., 2018) [4].

By examining these areas, the research seeks to provide insights that can inform public health policies and interventions designed to protect communities from the adverse effects of a changing climate.

Methodology

Study Design: This is a cross-sectional study aimed at assessing the health effects of climate change on the local population, focusing on the spread of infectious diseases, food security, and chronic health conditions.

Study Setting: The study will be conducted in the Department of Community Medicine at Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College and Hospital (ANMMCH), Gaya.

Study Duration: The study will be conducted over a period of 6 months.

Participants: A total of 300 participants will be included in this study. Participants will be selected from the local community through random sampling.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Residents of Gaya for at least the past 5 years.
2. Age between 18 and 65 years.
3. Willing to provide informed consent.
4. Able to comprehend and respond to the study questionnaire.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Individuals with cognitive impairments preventing them from completing the questionnaire.
2. Participants currently undergoing treatment for chronic diseases not related to climate change effects.

3. Pregnant women and nursing mothers.

Bias: Efforts will be made to minimize selection bias by employing random sampling techniques. Information bias will be reduced by using standardized and validated data collection instruments. Recall bias will be addressed by ensuring that participants are provided with clear and specific questions to facilitate accurate responses.

Data Collection: Data will be collected through structured interviews and questionnaires administered by trained personnel. The questionnaire will cover demographic information, health status, exposure to climate-related factors, incidence of infectious diseases, food security status, and chronic health conditions.

Procedure

1. Obtain ethical approval from the institutional review board.
2. Develop and pre-test the data collection instruments.
3. Train data collectors on study procedures and ethical considerations.
4. Conduct random sampling to select 300 participants from the local community.
5. Administer the questionnaires and conduct interviews in the Department of Community Medicine, ANMMCH.
6. Ensure data quality by cross-checking and verifying the collected data.

Statistical Analysis: Data will be analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize demographic information and health-related variables. Chi-square tests will be employed to examine associations between climate change effects and health outcomes. Logistic regression analysis will be performed to identify potential predictors of adverse health effects related to climate change. Significance will be set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Participant Demographics: A total of 300 participants were included in the study. The demographic distribution of the participants is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	N (%)
Age (years)	
18-30	90 (30%)
31-45	120 (40%)
46-65	90 (30%)
Gender	
Male	150 (50%)
Female	150 (50%)
Education Level	
No formal education	30 (10%)
Primary	60 (20%)
Secondary	120 (40%)
Higher	90 (30%)

Table 2: Climate-Related Factors and Health Outcomes

Variable	N (%)
Exposure to Extreme Heat Events	
Yes	180 (60%)
No	120 (40%)
Infectious Diseases	
Yes	90 (30%)
No	210 (70%)
Food Insecurity	
Yes	120 (40%)
No	180 (60%)
Chronic Health Conditions	
Yes	150 (50%)
No	150 (50%)

Table 2: Logistic Regression Analysis of Predictors of Adverse Health Outcomes

Predictor	B	SE	Wald	df	p-value	OR	95% CI for OR
Age	0.025	0.010	6.250	1	0.012	1.025	1.005 - 1.045
Gender (Female)	-0.150	0.220	0.470	1	0.493	0.861	0.565 - 1.312
Extreme Heat Exposure	0.590	0.260	5.142	1	0.023	1.804	1.090 - 2.987
Food Insecurity	0.750	0.290	6.707	1	0.010	2.117	1.198 - 3.742

Important results show a strong correlation between food insecurity and the occurrence of chronic health disorders, as well as between infectious illness incidence and exposure to extreme heat events. Three key indicators of poor health outcomes were found by logistic regression analysis: age, exposure to intense heat, and food insecurity.

Discussion

In order to evaluate the health effects of climate change, 300 people participated in a six-month study at the Department of Community Medicine. The study's primary focus was on infectious diseases, food security, and chronic health issues. A representative sample of the local community was guaranteed by the demographic distribution of participants, which was equally distributed across genders and age categories.

Significant correlations between variables related to climate change and health outcomes were found by the investigation. Notably, excessive heat episodes

were recorded by 60% of participants, while infectious infections were experienced by 30% of individuals. According to statistical studies, there is a significant correlation ($\chi^2(1) = 4.76$, $p = 0.029$) between exposure to severe heat and the occurrence of infectious diseases. This implies that those who are exposed to high temperatures have a higher risk of catching infectious diseases, either as a result of compromised immune systems or enhanced pathogen growth in warmer environments.

Forty percent of the individuals reported experiencing food insecurity, and fifty percent of them had chronic health issues. Food insecurity and chronic health disorders were significantly associated ($\chi^2(1) = 5.14$, $p = 0.023$). This suggests that those who experience food insecurity are more vulnerable to long-term health problems, most likely as a result of poor nutrition and associated stressors. Age, prolonged heat exposure, and food insecurity were also found to be significant predictors of

unfavourable health outcomes using logistic regression analysis.

In particular, there was a considerable correlation found between increased risks of health issues and exposure to intense heat (OR = 1.804, $p = 0.023$) and food insecurity (OR = 2.117, $p = 0.010$). The numerous ways that climate change affects public health are demonstrated by these findings, which also emphasise the pressing need for focused actions to lessen these effects.

The impact of climate change on crop yields, including altered temperatures and precipitation patterns, poses a threat to food security as well. More food instability and malnutrition may result from these changes, especially for vulnerable groups, as stressed by Tangcharoensathien et al. (2022) [5].

As it affects chronic health issues, food security, and infectious illnesses, climate change is becoming more widely acknowledged as a serious danger to public health. Viability and geographic range of disease vectors like ticks and mosquitoes are changing due to rising temperatures and altered precipitation patterns. The diseases Lyme, Dengue, Chikungunya, and Zika have spread to new areas as a result of this transition. Coates and colleagues, for example, point out that the expansion of *Aedes aegypti* mosquito range due to global warming is raising the danger of vector-borne diseases in places that were not previously impacted (Coates et al., 2019) [6]. In addition, it was observed that the connection between heat waves and a rise in the prevalence of illnesses related to the heat, cardiovascular conditions, and mental health problems brought on by stress and relocation (Patz, 2018). [7]

Conclusion

Conclusively, the study's findings illustrate the significant public health obstacles presented by climate change, specifically with respect to infectious diseases and chronic medical disorders. The study's noteworthy correlations and determinants underscore the need for all-

encompassing public health approaches and regulations that target mitigating the health risks associated with climate change, augmenting food security, and enhancing susceptible populations' ability to withstand extreme weather events.

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